

Open Data in Government

Cyril Voisin
Regional Technology Officer
Microsoft Gulf
[@cyrilvoisin](#)

Open Data around the World

“Release of public sector information creates opportunities for innovative use and reuse of data, and allows the commercial, research, and community sectors to add value.”

Australian Government [2013]

“It enables data-driven decision making: parliamentarians, policy makers, civil society organizations and individuals can see progress and make accurate, informed decisions on issues that affect people's lives.”

Kenya Open Data Initiative [2013]

“Openness will strengthen our democracy and promote efficiency and effectiveness in Government.”

Barack Obama, President of the United States [January 2009]

“The next generation of innovation in... academic research or public services will be possible because we find new ways to harness and learn from data.”

World Economic Forum [December 2013]

“It makes the government more accountable to citizens and strengthens our democracy. It brings us better public services and it feeds economic and social growth.”

Data.gov.uk [2013]

“By opening up more data, and through innovative use of technology, we can crowd-source ideas and co-create applications with the wider community.”

Tharman Shanmugaratnam, Singapore Deputy Prime Minister [April 2013]

“Not only are we making more effective decisions through improved use of data, but also involving communities, making them more informed and empowering them to deal with future challenges.”

World Economic Forum [January 2013]

Open Data Transforms Public Data Into...

Life-Saving Information

NYC officials could quickly create updated maps of evacuation centers and zones for Hurricane Sandy.

Quality of Life Apps

Apps provide on-demand info on restaurants, health facilities, jobs, transportation, and more.

Economic Prosperity

New York was named "The Most Economically Competitive City in the World" by the Economist Intelligence Unit.

Vibrant Developer Ecosystem

The annual BigApps Developer Contest awards \$50,000+ their favorite new apps. Every winner has gone on to launch a successful company.

Open Data worldwide adoption

Who leads the way in opening and utilizing open government data?

Open Data Platforms on Microsoft Azure

Turnkey cloud solution supporting government transparency

Microsoft® Azure™ is open, standards-based, and interoperable (with OData protocol one of many published APIs), helping governments:

- **Improve cost-efficiency** with cloud-based data management and hosting solutions
- **Provide citizen and developer access** to web tools to make data available and actionable
- **Gain access** to solution hosting through Microsoft Azure and consulting, deployment, and support services through leading Open Data solution providers
- **Eliminate infrastructure** and custom development, save staff time, and increase value provided through a turnkey cloud solution

*“Previously, we’d have to provision new servers to deal with an increase in users, but with **Windows Azure**, capacity is increased to deal with peaks in traffic, and is decreased as user numbers fall.”*

Ian Blackburn
Chief Executive Officer, BBits

Technologies & Solutions

Helping you harness the power of Open Data

Explore

 Office 365 Power BI

 Office

Surface™

 Windows Phone

 Windows

 Windows Azure

Manage

 Windows Azure
HDInsight & HDInsight
Server for Windows

 Microsoft
SQL Server™

 Microsoft
SQL Server™ 2008 R2
Parallel Data Warehouse

 Microsoft
System Center

Enrich

 Windows Azure
Marketplace

 Microsoft
SQL Server™

Insight

 Microsoft
SQL Server™
PowerPivot for Excel.

 Microsoft
SharePoint™
Power View

Socrata

Transform data assets into consumable information

Governments can provide cloud-based tools to optimize the data experience for any user context

Socrata Open Data Portal:

- Enables anywhere, anytime access to government data and services

Socrata GovStat:

- Cost-effective, turnkey Performance Management dashboard solution
- Helps you connect with citizens through community improvement goals

Socrata API Foundry:

- Industrializes API creation for data reuse, at 10% of the cost and time of custom development
- Helps you deliver developer-ready, open standards based APIs for all your data

CKAN Open Data Solution

Enable transparency through openness, interoperability, & OSS support

OKFN is a not-for-profit UK organization that developed the CKAN OSS product, a leading Open Data Catalogue and Indexing content management system running on Linux Ubuntu

CKAN Ver. 2 on Windows Azure

- Released on MS OpenTech VM Depot: [here](#)
- Windows Azure release CKAN blog: [here](#)
- Windows Azure hosts the CKAN Open Data Web, Catalogue Database Portal VMs and API CKAN Open data site examples:
 - data.gov.uk: UK government website CKAN integrated with Drupal and Windows Azure DataMarket hosting UK Weather open data dataset
 - USA data.gov with Socrata, Drupal OKFN CKAN information: [OKFN](#) and [CKAN](#)

bism@rt

Business Intelligence Solutions for Public Administration

Bigov: business intelligence tool that delivers city indicator information:

- Windows 8 City Dashboard app
- Business Intelligence Solution to help local governments
- Shows 80 city indicators proposed by The World Bank

BBits

Public Engagement Platform for Local Governments

Love Clean Streets: Award-winning service that enables anyone to upload photographs of environmental problems:

- Encourages engagement & action between citizens and local authorities
- Gives citizens the power to improve their immediate environment
- Citizens send in a report using free mobile app, a text or picture message, or via web site
- Local authorities deal with report and citizens are kept informed of progress

Reports Add Report Live Map Sign In How it Works **love clean streets** not signed in

Near More London, Camberwell, Greater London SE1 2, UK

bing
© 2010 Microsoft Corporation and
© 2010 Infomaps

0.5 miles

City Hall

[Vote Up](#)
0
[Vote Down](#)

Category		Reported	05/03/2010 12:52
Status		Response Required	Yes
Reported By	nigel.tyrell	Completed	No
Assigned To		Approved	Yes
		Assigned Name	

Permalink: <http://www.lovecleanstreets.org/Reports/Report/b8501bb5-0a57-4cce-9a93-19656e3cf7f8>

Subscribe to this report:

Esri

Cloud-based platform for maps & environmental data

Eye on Earth: Global public information network for environmental data:

- Users create and share environmentally relevant data and information online
- Interactive map-based visualizations
- Public-private partnership with European Environment Agency (EEA), Esri, and Microsoft

Windows 8 Government Apps

Enable Mobility for Field Inspectors

Deliver Public Services More Effectively

Foster Responsible Innovation

Region of Lombardia, Italy

“ We want to make information on government activities and decisions more open, comprehensive, timely, and freely available to the public. This is one step toward an open government model where we are more accountable and responsive to citizens.

Daniele Crespi, Innovative Services and eID Development Manager at Lombardia Informatica S.p.A.

Lombardia Open Data:
Designed for Growth

Business Challenges

The Regione Lombardia's dati.lombardia.it site needed to be able to host datasets on a wide variety of topics, such as museum locations for visitors, building energy efficiency ratings, and government spending information. The site needed to host more than 430 datasets and visualizations.

Solution

Moving to the Microsoft Azure platform shortened the distance between Lombardia's data and the end user. Socrata's publisher API automates data uploads to the portal, saving Lombardia time.

Customer Results / Benefits

More than 430 datasets and visualizations hosted on the portal
OpenApp competition attracted 111 app submissions and awarded €60,000 in prizes
Socrata's publisher API automates data uploads to the portal, saving time

[READ THE FULL CASE STUDY](#)

Microsoft has helped to transform data in data services [and] is helping us to improve our network. ”

Llius Sanz, I Marco, Director Información de Base en Institut Municipal d'Informàtica

City Expedites Service Delivery and Citizen Engagement

Business Challenges

The City of Barcelona has been using Microsoft technologies for more than 20 years. The city was looking for economic development through Open Data to secure new business within the city and enhance transparency, open government and help the economic point of view.

Solution

The Barcelona Open Data project was developed using Microsoft infrastructure technology and Microsoft Gold Partner Bismart. As part of the project, Bismart developed a Windows 8 City Dashboard app – Bigov Better City Indicators.

Customer Results / Benefits

New, faster network

Quickly answers critical government questions

Delivers public data through an open data database hosted in Microsoft Azure Cloud

Azure offers access to web services in an easy way

[READ THE FULL CASE STUDY](#)

LoveCleanStreets

“ The Windows development tools, the scalability of Windows Azure, and new features like the charms and tiles in Windows 8 give us more options than ever before for acting on our own ideas and those from our customers.

Ian Blackburn, Founder, Blackburn IT Services

Business Challenges

Efficiently collecting and responding to complaints about environmental crime is easier said than done. Call centers can be costly to operate, and websites used for reporting can be slow and cumbersome tools for quickly addressing issues.

Solution

BBITS created its free Love Clean Streets solution, available through the Windows 8 Marketplace and the Windows Phone Store. It lets people take pictures of neighborhood blight like vandalized buildings or “fly-tipping” – illegal garbage dumping.

Customer Results / Benefits

34 percent aggregate decrease in the use of call centers and less website reporting, and more use of the app.

Savings of £125,000 a year

87 percent reduction in the time it takes to process an issued reported, a 73 percent reduction in the amount of graffiti seen on the streets, and less than a day to clean up fly-tipping.

[READ THE FULL CASE STUDY](#)

Implementing a successful strategy

Policy

Solution

- Portal
- Publishing
- Visualization tools
- Apps

Next steps

Microsoft on Government Blog: www.microsoft.com/ongovernment

Microsoft Open Technologies: www.msopentech.com

Microsoft Open Government: www.microsoft.com/opengov

Open Data Example Sites

The image shows a screenshot of the Kenya Open Data website. On the right side, there is a large image of the Kenyan flag. To the left of the flag, there are four data categories, each with a green bar chart icon:

- Poverty Rate, by District**
Poverty Rate by District
- County Urbanization: Nairobi**
Census population by rural, urban, County estimates
- Local Authority Expenditures by Year: Nairobi**
Local Authority and Constituency Development Fund Expenditures, County estimates, Kenya Shillings
- Per Capita County Expenditures: Nairobi**
Local Authority and Constituency Development Fund Expenditures, County estimates, Kenya Shillings

Below these categories is a blue link: [Kenya Open Data](#)

"For the first time ever, people in our communities will be empowered to choose the best schools for their children, locate the nearest health facility that meets their needs, and use regional statistics to lobby their constituency representative for better infrastructure and services in their county"

Paul KuKubo, CEO of Kenya ICT Board [More...](#)

Open Government Data

- ▶ Weather conditions
- ▶ Prices and indices
- ▶ Social Insurance
- ▶ Trade (internal and external)
- ▶ Education and training
- ▶ Social services
- ▶ Agriculture and fishing
- ▶ Population and Housing
- ▶ Accounts Financial monetary affairs and Industry
- ▶ Health
- ▶ Energy and Water
- ▶ Transport and Communications

6:11 AM

[Saudi Open Data](#)

Shoothill

Interactive Warning System for Environmental Risks

FloodAlerts: Real-time flood warning and hydrometric data:

- Windows Azure, Bing Maps live map showing flood warnings in your Post Code
- 1st Social Networking UK Government solution via Facebook
- Shows the locations where Flood Alerts, Flood Warnings or Severe Flood Warnings are in force
- map is updated with information from our flood warning systems every 15 minutes

The first interactive warning system on Facebook to keep you informed about potential flood risks to your property.

Shoothill FloodAlerts beta

FloodAlerts

FloodAlerts is a free to use application developed by Shoothill and licensed by the Environment Agency, to provide Facebook users in England and Wales with flood warnings through their Facebook account.

FloodAlerts is the first graphical representation of the flood warning data which provides localised updates every 15 minutes, keeping users informed about the potential flood risks in their area.

When a flood alert is issued by the Environmental Agency, affecting the users monitored location; they will receive a notification on Facebook and to their registered Facebook email address. This alert will give users a direct link to the relevant flood warning (s) on the map, giving users a chance to assess the situation as it develops.

Shoothill

Shoothill are a leading software developer, specialising in online mapping solutions, data visualisation and interactive software applications for a diverse range of sectors, from transportation and the environment to media, advertising and telecommunications.

Go To FloodAlerts

Select Location to Monitor

tide level is 2.67 m AODN. The forecast wind direction is...

“ This is a fantastic example of private sector involvement in this important area, and shows how social media tools can be used for real-world benefit. ”

Richard Benyon MP, Parliamentary Under Secretary for Natural Environment, Water, and Rural Affairs

UK Environment Agency Uses Cloud Platform to Scale from 1 Million to 15.6 Million Hits

Business Challenges

The Environment Agency in the United Kingdom wanted to make its flood warning service more accessible to businesses and citizens by offering near real-time updates on areas at risk in England and Wales. More than 5 million people live or work in areas in danger of flooding.

Solution

Shoothill used Bing Maps—the only mapping system that includes Ordnance Survey data—and Windows Azure to create the FloodAlerts map using data from the Environment Agency nationwide network of monitoring stations.

Customer Results / Benefits

- Citizens stay one step ahead of floods, with 15.6 million hits in nine days
- Application wins innovation award
- Scalable solution proves highly resilient
- FloodAlerts gains recognition from UK Government

[READ THE FULL CASE STUDY](#)

Countries Committed to the Open Government Partnership

Multilateral initiative that aims to secure concrete commitments from governments to **promote transparency, empower citizens, fight corruption, and harness new technologies to strengthen governance.**

Governments Promoting Open Data

Hackathons, dashboards, & publishing data catalogues

Hackathon events around the world help drive innovations in Open Data:

- Citizens gather to write applications, liberate data, create visualizations, and publish analyses using open public data
- Encourages the adoption of open data policies by the world's local, regional, and national governments
- Drives innovation across Windows apps and devices

